

purified from ethanol. m. p. 189°, Yield 30% (Found : C, 74.13 ; H, 5.56 ; N, 14.23% ; $C_{18}H_{17}N_3O$ requires ; C, 74.22 ; H, 5.84 ; N, 14.43%).

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Chemical and Pharmacological Investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides*

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THE chemical investigation of *Pogestemon placranthoides*, revealed the presence of straight chain aliphatic hydrocarbon $C_{19}H_{40}$ and three sterols β -sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol. The pharmacological screening of the oil obtained from bracts, gave it's LD₅₀ 550 mg/kg. The oil also exhibited significant potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone, indicating a CNS depressant activity.

The plant *Pogestemon placranthoides* belongs¹ to family Labiatae and reported to possess² enormous medicinal properties.

The preliminary pharmacological screening of the oil, obtained from pet. ether extract of the plant, gave LD₅₀ value as 550 mg/kg i.p. The CNS depressant activity exhibited by the oil, was further substantiated by the significant potentiation of sleeping time induced by hexobarbitone.

A white low melting (m.p. 32°) aliphatic, straight chain hydrocarbon $C_{19}H_{40}$, was isolated from the oil. The identification of the hydrocarbon, was done with the help of combustion analysis and spectral data.

The chloroform extract of the plant furnished a colourless crystalline solid (m.p. 134-35°), which was identified to be β -sitosterol. The structure of β -sitosterol was ascertained by comparing the spectral data

with that of authentic sample and preparation of derivative.

Though T.L.C. showed β -sitosterol to be homogeneous in nature, mass spectrum revealed it to be a mixture of three compounds, with molecular peaks at 414, 412 and 400. The interpretation of the mass spectrum showed that along with β -sitosterol, other two compounds present were campesterol (M^+ 400) and stigmasterol (M^+ 412).

This is in agreement with the observations made by earlier workers^{3,4} that whenever these sterols co-exist in nature it is extremely difficult to separate them to mass spectral purity.

Analysis of the ash of the plant showed the presence of iron and calcium. The presence of calcium salt may be quite significant in the light of antihemorrhagic properties possessed⁵ by calcium salt and the similar activity exhibited by the plant.

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Search for Possible Anti-Protozoal Compounds in the Quinoxaline Series

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QUINOXALINES having different substitutions are reported to possess wide range of antiprotozoal activity^{1,2}. Investigation on the amebicidal activity of quinoxaline 1,4-(N,N')-dioxides and its substituted compounds³, showed that the compounds were effective in acute amebic dysentery in man although none of them could be used due to toxic side effects. On the other hand many 1-substituted 4 or 5-imidazole derivatives are known to be active against *T. vaginalis*

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